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The Positive Role of Attitude Toward of Vendor in Mediating the Relationship Between Vendor Cognition and Advertise Cognition on Vendor Usage Intention

Nanda Farhanah¹, Budhi Haryanto²

^{1,2} Master of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Surakarta, Indonesia

Correspondence: Nanda Farhanah, Master of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Surakarta, 57126, Indonesia. Email: nandafarhanah@student.uns.ac.id

Abstract

This article aims to explain the influence of vendor cognition and advertise cognition on vendor usage intention mediated by positive attitude towards of vendor. The literature review was conducted to identify the variables that build the conceptual model. The expected findings are that there is a positive relationship between vendor perception and positive attitude towards vendor usage intentions and a positive relationship between advertise cognitive and positive attitude towards vendor usage intentions. This study also explains the dimensions of familiarity, credibility, and trust that produce vendor cognition. Furthermore, this study also explains the dimensions of entertain, creativity, and informative that produces advertise cognition. This study provides an alternative conceptual model in the field of consumer behavioral. Researchers hope this research can provide an understanding to wedding marketers to design effective marketing strategies to influence potential consumers. This paper is also expected to contribute theoretically, practically and possibly can be used for future studies.

Keywords: Vendor Perception, Advertise Cognition, Vendor Usage Intention

1. Introduction

The Covid-19 that has occurred in Indonesia since March 2020 has disrupted many things, including the trend of marriage. The implementation of *Pembatasan Sosial Berskala Besar* (PSBB) in 2020 regulates various public activities including wedding ceremony that the rules limit the number of guests who can attend wedding receptions (bbc.com, 2020). Wedding vendor companies need to adapt by shifting their sales strategy to digital marketing, including by utilizing social media platforms to interact with their potential customers (sindonews.com, 2021).

Instagram became the third most popular social media in Indonesia according to the GWI Survey in the third quarter of 2020 (BeritaSatu.com, 2021) with the dominance of the age range of its users being 18-24 years old, which we usually call Gen-Z with a total of 63 million users (Katadata.co.id, 2021). According to Katadata.co.id (2020), since March 2020, public social media access has increased by 70%. Consumers choose social media as a reference for information in the form of public opinions and recommendations (Fu et al., 2020) to decide on the purchase of a product or service which is of course in contrast to a few years ago when people trusted direct purchases by visiting the offline store (Katadata.co.id, 2020).

Researchers found that many previous studies explained the impact of advertise cognition and brand cognition on consumer behavioral intentions. First, Alalwan (2018) argues that social media promotion is communication that shapes the decision-making process by consumers. This research was conducted in Jordan with the language used as Arabic so language adjustments were made on the questionnaire with a seven-point Likert scale in its measurement. The researcher uses six variables such as performance expectations, hedonic motivation, habits, interactivity, informativeness and perceived relevance as variables that influence the purchase intention. And besides the habit variable, all of these variables are supported to significantly influence the consumer's purchase intention. Social media is considered to provide an opportunity for companies to interact directly with consumers and the big data that can track, map and target consumer behavior that strengthen the company's marketing strategy (Katadata.co.id, 2020).

Companies need to improve consumer perceptions of brands related to emotional bonds such as the trust dimension (Atulkar, 2020). The questionnaire in this study is distributed in a shopping center in India. The results of this study indicate that variables such as quality, value and customer satisfaction can lead to consumer confidence in a brand and generate consumer loyalty so that all hypotheses are supported. Consumer reviews such as testimonials can be used as advertisements to increase consumer trust in the brand (J. Lee et al., 2011). Social media advertising is an effective, easy, inexpensive and targeted way to attract potential consumers (Nasir et al., 2021). This research questionnaire was distributed online in Turkey.

So the author researched a study to determine the positive relationship between vendor cognition and positive attitude towards vendor to vendor usage intention and positive relationship between advertise cognition and positive attitude towards vendor towards vendor usage intention. This study also explains the dimensions of familiarity, credibility, and trust that produce vendor cognition. In addition, this study also explains the entertainment, creativity, and informative dimensions that shape the vendor perception of the prospective bride and groom in the Gen-Z age range in choosing wedding vendors.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Core Theory

The conceptual model is constructed based on cognitive psychological theory. Cognitive psychology theory explains that consumer behavior consists of 3 structures, such as the first is the cognitive structure which is perceptions as a result of the thinking process. Furthermore, the affective structure is in the form of feelings of liking or disliking something as a result of the process. And the last is the cognitive structure, which is an intention to behave as a form of the process of acting (Schiffman et al., 2011). The existence of marketing communication has an effect on cognitive, affective and behavioral attitudes among Gen Z (Duffett, 2017).

Its application in the formation of a conceptual model of advertise cognition which has the dimensions of entertainment, creativity, and informative as well as variable vendor cognition with dimensions of familiarity, credibility and trust is a cognitive psychological structure that produces an affective structure in the form of a positive attitude toward vendors and a constructive structure in the form of vendor usage intention.

2.2 Vendor Cognition

Brand names can increase brand awareness and create brand perceptions for consumers that increase customer satisfaction and loyalty and help companies in terms of setting premium prices, loyalty and positive word of mouth (Muruganatham et al., 2017). It is necessary to clearly communicate aspects of brand product quality because consumer perceptions of brand quality are the most important thing in purchase intentions (Walsh et al., 2012).

Consumer cognition vendors are formed when a brand has good credibility with the conformity of the promised quality with what consumers receive (Srivastava et al., 2020). The existence of brand credibility in communicating its products and consumer familiarity with a brand contributes to generating consumer loyalty in making repeated purchases and WOM attitudes (Maia Bairaada et al., 2021). Another study conducted in Malaysia states that when credibility is well established from F&B vendors, it can lead to consumer trust which has an effect on positive attitudes of consumer satisfaction (Tseng et al., 2022).

2.3 Familiarity

Familiarity with a brand or product plays an important role in consumer decision making (Kuhzady et al., 2020). The complexity of online transactions makes consumers reluctant to transact, but when consumers feel familiar with brands, they tend to seek information and consumers feel more familiar when brands often appear in advertisements (McClure et al., 2020). Fu et al. (2020) said that familiarity can have a positive effect on shopping intentions when there is involvement between consumers and products that motivates consumers to evaluate the products offered. Informative advertising about a product can generate trust and familiarity with the product and brand in the minds of consumers (Copeland et al., 2020). When consumers find the familiarity about a brand and good credibility of the brand can result in consumer loyalty in making repeated purchases and WOM attitudes (Maia Bairaada et al., 2021).

2.4 Credibility

Credibility in the minds of consumers is formed when a brand is able to fulfill promises in its advertisements and help consumers build brand perceptions (Srivastava et al., 2020). Advertising content can be in the form of a claim to the credibility of a product that denies the superior features of competing brand products (Schiffman et al., 2011). When a brand has good credibility, the brand can create value by reducing advertising costs and reducing the level of perceived risk by increasing the conception of the quality of the products produced (Srivastava et al., 2020). The existence of a brand's credibility accompanied by a product quality that is well known by consumers can result in a positive consumer attitude (Tseng et al., 2022). High or low credibility of a company can be obtained from sponsored advertising content displayed by marketers and this affects the cognitive and affective structure of consumers in responding it (Li et al., 2020).

2.5 Trust

Consumer loyalty and purchase intentions are formed on the existence of consumer trust in a product (Calvo Porral & Levy-Mangin, 2016). Trust is a belief that comes from his perception of certain attributes (Muruganatham et al., 2017). Trust in the brand is formed on an emotional bond (Atulkar, 2020). Brand trust is a consumer's expectation of a brand to fulfill promises (Huaman et al., 2019). The research of Tong et al. (2018) argues that consumer gender demographics shape perceptions that influence product purchase intention behavior. Atulkar (2020) argues that companies need to improve customer perceptions of brands related to emotional ties such as by targeting age groups as well as customer income which results in customer loyalty to the brand.

Consumer trust can be formed from honest comments such as testimonials from consumers who have used the product (J. Lee et al., 2011). So this can be an effective advertising method. Consumer trust in a brand also can be arises from detailed product information and entertaining advertisements (Kim et al., 2010). The livestreaming feature on social media can be used by marketers to build consumer engagement so as to create consumer confidence in the brand (Wongkitrungrueng & Assarut, 2020). Consumer trust in an online brand significantly

affects consumers' positive attitudes (Nosi et al., 2021). Consumer trust can be formed from the good credibility of a product and brand that can produce a positive consumer attitude (Tseng et al., 2022). Consumer loyalty arises when consumers have trust in a brand even though the product being sold is a food product that is perishable product such as pastry (Rahman et al., 2022).

2.6 Advertise Cognition

In increasing consumers' purchase intentions towards brands, marketers need to create positive attitudes by using attractive and appropriate advertisements (Gahlot et al., 2019). The advertising style used can evoke a customer's self-image which can influence purchase intentions (Zeng et al., 2020). Social media is considered to be a source of relevant information for consumers so that the advertisements displayed can motivate consumers to make purchases (Alalwan, 2018). Other studies say there is a significant impact of the attractiveness of advertising content on social media on consumers in Pakistan who are under 40 years old. So that a differentiation strategy in marketing is needed by marketers to increase consumers' positive attitudes (Palalic et al., 2020). Unique online advertisements with informative and entertaining dimensions can increase smartphone sales in Bangladesh (Mustafi & Hosain, 2020).

2.7 Entertain

Advertisements must be made in an entertaining, interesting and fun way by displaying funny animations and unique and creative packaging to attract the attention and interest of consumers (Sari et al., 2020). Consumers assume that when the level of personalization of an advertising content is higher, the possibility that consumers are interested in the ad can be higher (Setyani et al., 2019). A study states that informative and entertaining advertisements are positively related to purchase intentions in case studies of environmentally friendly products (Hosseinkhah Choshaly & Mirabolghasemi, 2022). An advertisement that is made entertainingly can increase consumer confidence in a brand which of course results in a positive attitude and consumer purchase intention (Kim et al., 2010). Entertaining advertisements can influence consumer interest and result in purchase intentions for fast food restaurant products in the Middle East (Hanaysha, 2022).

2.8 Creativity

Alalwan (2018) argues that the hedonic motivation in consumers makes companies have to be able to design and develop their advertisements more innovatively and creatively. Consumers perceive advertising content as more creative when marketers can design content more personally so that it can be more relevant to consumers (Setyani et al., 2019). Consumers will be more attracted to an advertisement when the advertisement is packaged creatively by marketers (Sari et al., 2020). The creativity of an advertisement in creating content, such as in the form of storytelling, can attract consumers' interest (Karampournioti & Wiedmann, 2021).

2.9 Informative

High-reputation companies carry out a mixed pricing strategy where when consumers understand about the occurrence of intense competition, high-reputation companies carry out lower price reductions than low-reputation companies (Liu et al., 2012). Millennial consumers use social media as a source of information and perceive an advertisement as a reliable source of information about the product to be purchased (Sari et al., 2020). Customers are motivated to buy products when they perceive advertising on social media as a viable source of information (Alalwan, 2018).

Consumer trust and familiarity can be formed when an informative advertisement about the product quality of a brand and generate product purchase intentions (Copeland et al., 2020). The technique of creating emotional content in the form of storytelling can be applied by online marketers to increase the attractiveness of consumers to visit and have an impact on consumers' positive attitudes in the form of willingness to pay higher prices (Karampournioti & Wiedmann, 2021). Research in Malaysia states that informative social media advertising has a significant relationship with the intention to use Islamic banking products (Mohd Thas Thaker et al., 2021).

2.10 Positive Attitude Towards of Vendors

Consumer attitudes towards an advertising framing depend on the character of consumers and the products offered by a brand (Schiffman et al., 2011). A product advertisement can reach blog consumers when there is advertising content with attractive, entertaining designs and has credibility, is trustworthy and honest because blog consumers have the same interests as ad creators (van Esch et al., 2018). The existence of attractive advertisements with creative and entertaining content can form a positive attitude of consumers (Setyani et al., 2019). Advertising content with elements of humor can increase consumer engagement and positive attitudes towards a brand (Schiffman et al., 2011). The positive attitude of consumers can be formed from the creativity of marketers in creating storytelling advertising content (Karampournioti & Wiedmann, 2021). Research on fast food restaurants in the Middle East mentions the influence of informative and entertaining advertising and brand involvement on positive consumer attitudes that result in consumer purchase intentions (Hanaysha, 2022).

2.11 Vendor Usage Intention

The existence of advertising content that is entertaining and provides information can shape consumer purchase intentions where the advertising content presented affects consumer attitudes toward the brand (E. B. Lee et al., 2017). Consumer attitudes are influenced by advertisements presented by a brand on its social media (Alalwan, 2018). When a brand succeeds in creating a positive consumer attitude by creating attractive advertising content, this can increase purchase intention (Gahlot Sarkar et al., 2019). Brand recognition in the form of information that has a significant effect on consumers' emotions in the form of positive attitudes and consumer decision making in the form of purchase intentions (Song et al., 2020).

3. Hypothesis and Conceptual Model

Based on the problems described above, a hypothesis is needed to make research and problem solving more focused. The hypotheses in this study are as follows:

3.1. The relationship between vendor cognition and positive attitude toward vendor

When consumers trust in a brand, they can be loyal and intend to make a purchase (Calvo Porral & Levy-Mangin, 2016). But sometimes the complexity of online transactions makes consumers reluctant to transact but when they feel the familiarity with the brand, it can encourage consumers to seek information about a brand's product on social media (McClure & Seock, 2020). Consumers have a tendency to decide to make a purchase when they have a positive perception of a brand based on a positive image and positive attitude assessment that has a positive impact on purchasing (Schiffman et al., 2011). The perception of credibility is formed when a brand can fulfill its promise in advertising (Srivastava et al., 2020). Meanwhile, customer trust in a brand is formed on the emotional bond between the customer and the brand (Atulkar, 2020). So companies need to improve customer perceptions of brands related to emotional ties such as by targeting age groups and customer income which results in customer loyalty to the brand (Atulkar, 2020).

Consumers assess advertising content from companies with high credibility that can generate positive attitudes and consumer behavioral intentions towards brands (Li et al., 2020). Consumer awareness of the brand underlies consumers to make purchases so that marketers need the ability to clearly communicate the quality of brand products (Walsh et al., 2012). The existence of social interaction in the form of familiarity has a positive effect on shopping intentions because of the involvement between consumers and products that motivates to evaluate the product. So it can be said that consumer perceptions of vendor brands in social media advertisements can produce positive consumer attitudes towards a vendor. Then a hypothesis is proposed in the form of:

H1: vendor cognition will have a positive effect on positive attitude toward vendor

3.2. The relationship between advertise cognition and positive attitude toward vendor

Advertising can affect a consumer's attitude by forming feelings (affection) and assessment (cognition) of consumer beliefs in a brand (Schiffman et al., 2011). In line with the research of Teng et al. (2007) which states that affective responses to consumers play a significant role in consumer evaluations of advertisements received from a brand. Funny and interesting advertising content with creative packaging can form positive consumer attitudes towards brands (Sari et al., 2020). Consumers consider social media to be a relevant reference source for consumers to make purchases (Alalwan, 2018). When marketers create personalized advertisements according to consumer interests, it will increase the positive attitude of consumers in the form of purchase intentions (Setyani et al., 2019). So marketer need to be creative to make a good advertise (Modig et al., 2014).

The positive attitude of consumers towards an advertisement depends on the relevance of the consumer's character to the product offered (Schiffman et al., 2011). Informative social media advertising has a significant relationship with the intention to use Islamic banking products in Malaysia (Mohd Thas Thaker et al., 2021). Entertaining and informative advertisements can influence consumer interest and result in purchase intentions for fast food restaurant products in the Middle East (Hanaysha, 2022). From the research that has been done, the second hypothesis is produced in the form of:

H2: advertise cognition will have a positive effect on positive attitude toward vendor

3.3. The relationship between positive attitude toward vendor and vendor usage intention

Advertising content with elements of humor can increase consumer engagement and positive attitudes towards a brand (Schiffman et al., 2011). Research (Uribe et al., 2022) states that the existence of a brand attitude on celebrity endorsements encourages buying interest in brand products. Research shows that entertainment, informativeness and credibility have an effect on consumer attitude and behavioral intention (Yang et al., 2017). The research of Schiffman et al. (2011) states that there is a tendency when consumers like an advertisement, consumers tend to buy the product. Consumers consider social media to be a suitable and reliable source of information for consumers so as to form positive attitudes that can influence consumers to make purchases (Alalwan, 2018). Research on tourism marketers in Tunisia shows that there is a significant relationship between informative and entertaining advertising and brand credibility on positive consumer attitudes and influence on brand reputation (Hamouda, 2018). From these studies, the third hypothesis is obtained, namely:

H3: positive attitude toward vendor will have a positive effect on vendor usage intention

3.4. Conceptual Model

Based on the development of the conceptualized hypothesis, FIGURE 1 below is the resulting conceptual model framework.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model about Behavioral Process in Vendor Usage Intention

In this conceptual framework, the motivation behind the desire to use vendors such as familiarity, credibility and trust in a vendor's brand and also the existence of advertising cognition in the form of entertaining content, creativity in advertising packaging and informative advertising content. When consumers start to believe in a brand through a positive brand image, advertising can build brand perception and consumers can remember the product and brand when making a purchase (Kaur & Hundal, 2017).

4. Conclusion

This conceptual model provides an alternative model that is different from previous research, such as one of the most important factors influencing the perception of young consumers, namely trust (Tong et al., 2018). In addition, consumers perceive advertising content that is creative and relevant to consumer tastes will produce a positive consumer attitude so that it can streamline promotional costs incurred by the company (Setyani et al., 2019). The dimension of familiarity with a brand or product plays an important role in consumer decision making (Kuhzady et al., 2020). Marketers need to increase consumer perceptions of brands related to emotional ties such as the dimensions of trust by targeting age groups and customer income which results in customer loyalty to the brand (Atulkar, 2020). Social media advertising is an effective, easy, inexpensive and targeted way to attract potential consumers (Nasir et al., 2021).

This model is a role model that can be used as a reference and applied to the phenomenon of the intention to use wedding vendors. Practically, this study provides an understanding for vendors to increase positive attitudes and intentions to use vendors by paying attention to variables such as vendor cognition and advertise cognition, each of which has dimensions such as vendor cognition paying attention to the dimensions of familiarity, credibility and trust and advertise cognition paying attention to dimensions of attractiveness of advertisements such as entertainment, creativity and informative.

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